

Impacts of the Inflation Reduction Act on the Economics of Clean Hydrogen and Synthetic Liquid Fuels

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Abstract:

The Inflation Reduction Act (IRA) in the United States provides unprecedented incentives for deploying low-carbon hydrogen and liquid fuels, among other low greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions technologies. To better understand the prospective competitiveness of low-carbon or negative-carbon hydrogen and liquid fuels under the IRA in the early 2030s, we examine the impacts of IRA provisions on costs of producing hydrogen and synthetic liquid fuel made from natural gas, electricity, short-cycle biomass (agricultural residues), and corn-ethanol. With IRA credits (45V or 45Q), but excluding incentives provided by other national or state policies, hydrogen produced by electrolysis using carbon-free electricity (green H₂) and natural gas reforming with carbon capture and storage (CCS) (blue H₂) are cost-competitive with the carbon-intensive benchmark gray H₂ from steam methane reforming. Biomass-derived H₂ with or without CCS is not cost-competitive under current IRA provisions. However, if IRA allowed biomass gasification with CCS to claim a 45V credit for carbon-neutral H₂ and a 45Q credit for negative biogenic-CO₂ emissions, this pathway would be less costly than gray H₂. The IRA credit for clean fuels (45Z), currently stipulated to end in 2027, would need to be extended, or similar policy support provided by other national or state policies, for clean synthetic liquid fuel to be cost-competitive with petroleum-derived liquid fuels. Levelized IRA subsidies per unit of CO₂ mitigated for all hydrogen and synthetic liquid fuel production pathways, except electricity-derived synthetic liquid fuel, range from 65 to 384 \$/t CO₂, which is within or below the range in U.S. federal government estimates of the Social Cost of Carbon (SCC) in the 2030 to 2040 timeframe.

Synopsis statement: Prospective cost-competitiveness of clean hydrogen and liquid fuels versus conventional fossil-fuel derived alternatives under the Inflation Reduction Act

Keywords: Inflation Reduction Act (IRA); Energy Policy; Hydrogen; Synthetic liquid fuels; Bioenergy with carbon capture and storage (BECCS); Electrofuels; Economics

Introduction:

In the United States, a commitment to cut greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions to half of the peak levels by 2030 and to net-zero by mid-century has become a major driver for new laws to accelerate the clean energy transition¹⁻³. The Inflation Reduction Act (IRA) of 2022 provides unprecedented incentives for deploying low GHG emission technologies. The incentives include investment and production tax credits (ITCs and PTCs) designed to encourage businesses to invest in clean energy technologies.* The IRA tax credits and other mechanisms are projected to result in an estimated \$370 billion, and potentially more, of federal government outlays toward this goal over ten years (2023-2032)⁴, including 45V credits for hydrogen produced with life cycle carbon intensity below 4 kg CO₂e/kg H₂, 45Q credits for CO₂ capture, utilization, and storage (CCUS), 40B and 45Z credits for low-carbon emission liquid fuels, and 48D and 45Y credits for carbon-free electricity generation, e.g., from nuclear, wind, or solar. The IRA

* “Clean” in this paper is short-hand for low-carbon or negative-carbon emissions. Other factors, such as criteria air pollutants (e.g., NO_x, SO_x, and particulate matter) are not considered in the analysis.

also stipulates penalties for emissions of methane from specific types of facilities, primarily in the oil and gas sector^{5,6}.

Several macro-energy system modeling studies have estimated that investments stimulated by the IRA would help to reduce U.S. GHG emissions to 33 – 40% below 2005 levels by 2030⁷⁻¹⁰. These studies estimate that GHG emission reductions under the new law come largely from the decarbonization of the power sector via wind and solar power generation^{7,8}. The Act significantly boosts investment in wind power and solar PV, almost doubling the annual capital investment from \$181 billion under existing policy (i.e., no IRA) to \$334 billion in 2030⁷. In addition to investment in the power sector, modeling results also show the IRA driving annual capital investments of \$60 billion by 2035 in hydrogen and \$30 billion in synthetic liquid fuel (SLF), including electrofuels and biomass-derived SLF⁷.

Many modeling studies emphasize the crucial roles of hydrogen and SLF in clean energy transitions¹¹⁻¹³. H₂ is currently an important feedstock used in ammonia production and oil refining¹⁴. In addition to existing demands, H₂ has the potential to play a critical role in decarbonizing steel production^{12,15}, power generation^{12,16}, transportation¹⁷, and the petrochemical industry,^{12,18} among others. For example, steel produced by clean H₂-based direct reduction of iron - electric arc furnace processes result in 60% GHG emissions reduction as compared to conventional blast furnace-basic oxygen furnaces¹⁵. Biofuels and SLF can be drop-in alternatives to petroleum-derived liquid fuels (e.g., jet fuel, diesel, and gasoline). Since SLF can generally be utilized without requiring radical changes to fuel distribution and usage systems, they represent promising paths to displacing petroleum-derived liquid fuels for heavy-duty trucks, ships, and aircraft, thus reducing hard-to-abate emissions from the transportation sector¹².

Currently, natural gas reforming is the primary process for hydrogen production in the U.S., with life cycle GHG emissions of 10-12 kg CO₂e/kg H₂, depending on the conversion efficiency and level of upstream methane emissions¹⁹. Direct use of petroleum-derived liquid fuels (e.g., jet fuel, distillates, and gasoline) accounts for about 88% of U.S. transportation fuel usage, while biofuel (primarily corn-derived ethanol) accounts for 5%²⁰. Without policy support, nascent clean H₂ and SLF production technologies today are not competitive with their carbon-intensive fossil-fuel counterparts. The IRA and other policy support is aimed at helping clean options gain early footholds in markets, scale-up commercial deployment, and achieve cost reductions via economies of scale, experience, and incremental innovation, as support policies have achieved for other technologies, e.g., wind generation²¹.

In our previous study²², we analyzed technologies for H₂ and Fischer-Tropsch liquid (FTL) production and determined their environmental and economic performance in the context of an assumed universally-applied carbon tax. Here, building on that work, we seek to provide a timely and nuanced analysis of specific provisions of the IRA affect the cost-competitiveness of low-carbon and negative carbon hydrogen and SLF production relative to carbon-intensive fossil fuel equivalents. The needed energy transition will be facilitated if clean H₂ and SLF are less costly to produce than fossil fuel counterparts. Other policies, including the federal Renewable Fuel Standard (RFS)²³ and California's Low Carbon Fuel Standard (LCFS)²⁴, have been promoted clean fuels production for transportation prior to passage of the IRA. Credit values under these programs have fluctuated significantly during the past 10 years, ranging from 0.05 – 3 \$/RIN in the RFS program²⁵, and 20 to 210 \$/t CO₂ in the LCFS program²⁶, as discussed in Section S2 of the Supplemental Information (SI).[†] Fuel producers can collect these incentives in combination with IRA credits, and we also assess potential outcomes of doing so.

In this article, we present plant-level techno-economic assessments to determine the levelized cost of fuel production (LCOF) for each of 15 different clean hydrogen or SLF production technological pathways (Table 1), taking into consideration provisions of the IRA (Supporting Information (SI), Table S1), RFS, and LCFS. We compare the LCOFs of clean H₂ and SLF with production costs of equivalent

[†] Unless otherwise indicated all prices and costs in this paper are in 2022 dollars.

fossil benchmarks (gray H₂ and petroleum-derived liquid fuel). The timeframe of relevant IRA credits, their monetary values, and relevant statutory requirements are summarized in Table S1.

We seek to answer the following questions regarding clean hydrogen and clean liquid fuels:

- (1) Can the IRA incentives make them competitive on a production-cost basis in the 2030 timeframe with conventional, carbon-intensive fossil-fuel based equivalents?
- (2) Does the IRA appear to favor some production technology pathways over others?
- (3) Are there shortcomings in the design of the IRA incentives for production of these, and if so, what modifications might help mitigate those?

Table 1. Summary of evaluated technologies for H₂ and SLF production and applicable policies.

	Technology¹	Feedstock	Relevant IRA credits²	Other policy³
<u>Hydrogen (H₂)</u>				
P1 SMR	Steam methane reforming	Natural gas ⁴	N/A	N/A
P2 SMR-CCS	Steam methane reforming w/CCS	Natural gas ⁴	45Q or 45V	N/A
P3 ATR-CCS	Autothermal reforming w/CCS	Natural gas ⁴	45Q or 45V	N/A
P4 Electrolysis	Electrolysis	Elec. (wind/solar) ⁵	45V	N/A
P5 BG-H2	Gasifier + water-gas-shift	Biomass ⁶	45V	N/A
P6 BGCCS-H2	Gasifier + water-gas-shift w/CCS	Biomass ⁶	45Q or 45V	N/A
<u>Synthetic Liquid Fuels (SLF)⁷</u>				
<i>Synthesis from clean H₂ and carbon-neutral CO₂</i>				
P7 SMR-SLF	SMR-CCS + reverse water-gas-shift-Fischer Tropsch synthesis (RWGS-FTS)	H ₂ (P2), CO ₂ DAC (direct air capture) ⁸	45Q or 45V for H ₂ , 45Q for CO ₂ from DAC, 45Z	LCFS
P8 ATR-SLF	ATR-CCS + RWGS-FTS	H ₂ (P3), CO ₂ DAC ⁸	45Q or 45V for H ₂ , 45Q for DAC, 45Z	LCFS
P9 Elec-SLF	Electrolysis + RWGS-FTS	H ₂ (P4), CO ₂ DAC ⁸	45V for H ₂ , 45Q for DAC, 45Z	LCFS
P10 BG-SLF	BG-H2 + RWGS-FTS	H ₂ (P5), bio-CO ₂	45V for H ₂ , 45Z	LCFS
P11 BGCCS-SLF	BGCCS-H2 + RWGS-FTS	H ₂ (P6), bio-CO ₂	45Q or 45V for H ₂ , 45Z	LCFS
<i>Integrated biomass-gasification/FT synthesis</i>				
P12 Int. Bio-SLF	Integrated biogasifier-FTS	Biomass	45Z	RFS (D3), ¹⁰ LCFS
P13 Int. BioCCS-SLF	Integrated biogasifier-FTS w/ CCS	Biomass	45Q or 45Z	RFS (D3), ¹⁰ LCFS
<i>Ethanol-to-Synthetic liquid fuel</i>				
P14 EtOH-SLF	Corn-ethanol ⁹ to SLF	Corn-ethanol	N/A	RFS (D6), ¹⁰ LCFS
P15 EtOHCCS-SLF	Corn-ethanol ⁹ w/ CCS to SLF	Corn-ethanol w/ CCS	45Q and 45Z	RFS (D5), ¹⁰ LCFS

1. Pathways P1-P6 and P12-P13 represent production occurring at single facilities exploiting the single most remunerative IRA incentive among those for which they are eligible. The IRA disallows any one facility from claiming more than one of 45V, 45Q, and 45Z credits. Pathways P7-P9 are assumed to consist of 3 facilities each, which enables these pathways to incorporate 3 separate IRA credits: 45V or 45Q for H₂ production, 45Q for direct air capture, and 45Z for SLF production. Pathways P10-P11 each include two facilities, one producing H₂ and CO₂ from biomass and garnering 45V or 45Q credits and the other combining

H₂ and CO₂ from the first facility to synthesize liquid fuels and collect 45Z credits. Similarly, pathway P15 includes capture of fermentation CO₂ at a standalone ethanol facility claiming 45Q for CCS, and a separate ethanol to SLF facility claiming 45Z.

2. In addition to these listed credits, our analysis embeds IRA 45Y credits for clean electricity production into the assumed electricity price for pathway P4 and the IRA's stipulated penalties for methane emissions into the assumed natural gas price for pathways P1-P3. (See Table S1 for descriptions of IRA credits.) All pathways are assumed to satisfy prevailing wage and apprenticeship requirements and thus qualify for the maximum level of credit within a given type of IRA credit.

3. Other policies considered in this study are the LCFS and RFS, but only for the SLF pathways. Hydrogen used in transport may be eligible for LCFS credits²⁷, but we do not consider this option (see Limitations section of the paper). The P7-P15 pathways produce drop-in transportation fuels, and we assume all are eligible for LCFS credits. Integrated biomass-gasifier-FTS (P12 and P13) are eligible for RFS since they produce SLF directly from lignocellulosic biomass.

4. We assume upstream natural gas emissions of 1.7% (0.29 g of methane per MJ of delivered natural gas)²⁸. The IRA methane emissions penalty is \$1500/tonne starting in 2025 (Table S1). We reflect this in the natural gas price assumed in our analysis (\$ 4.3/GJ, see Table S3). Upstream life cycle upstream GHG emissions of natural gas are 13.8 kg CO₂/GJ_{HHV} (Table S4) and its carbon content is 50 kg CO₂/GJ_{HHV} (Table S5)

5. The electrolysis pathway is assumed to use wind- and/or solar-derived electricity as input. The 45Y clean electricity PTC is incorporated into the electricity price assumed in our analysis. The input electricity price after applying the 45Y subsidy is \$ 21.5/MWh (see Table S3) and the capacity factor for electrolysis is 0.55^{13, 22}.

6. The biomass used here is assumed to be agricultural residues, and we treat its biogenic CO₂ to be carbon-neutral, consistent with its treatment in the billion-ton study.²⁹ Upstream (non-biogenic) emissions of 5.08 kg CO₂/GJ (Table S4) are assumed from harvesting, transport, and pre-processing. The delivered cost of the biomass is 6.1 \$/GJ (Table S3), and its carbon content is 87.9 kg CO₂/GJ_{HHV} (Table S5).

7. A variety of SLF compositions are possible, depending on process design. Here we assume the composition to be 82% synthetic paraffinic kerosene (SPK) and 18% naphtha (lower heating value basis), which is composition determined in a prior detailed process modeling study involving one of this paper's authors³⁰.

8. For P7-P9, the requisite carbon-neutral CO₂ input is assumed to be from direct air capture (DAC) powered by renewable energy. The IRA's 45Q credit (130 \$/t CO₂ for 12 years) is applied to reduce the cost of CO₂ from DAC, giving CO₂ costs of 164 \$/t CO₂ (see note *e* in Table S3).

9. The corn-ethanol is assumed to be 90% from dry mills and 10% from wet mills (the US industry average from GREET³¹), with a delivered cost of \$1.83/gal (Table S3). For corn-ethanol with CCS, CO₂ from fermentation is compressed transported, and stored at an added cost of 45\$/t CO₂ (Table S3).

10. Pathways P12 and P13 can claim RFS cellulosic biofuel (D3) credits. Pathways P14 and P15 are eligible for RFS renewable fuel (D6) and advanced biofuel (D5) credits, respectively, based on the GHG emissions reductions they provide.

Method:

The timeframe for relevant IRA credits, their values for different carbon intensity products, and other relevant statutory requirements are summarized in Table S1. Building on details provided in our previous study²², the performances and costs of technologies prospectively commercially deployed in the early 2030s are summarized in Table 2. Table S2 provides additional details. For pathways P1 through P11 we used performance and cost data and methods from our previous study (Table 2), but with adjustments to LCOF calculations to incorporate the impact of provisions of the IRA (Table S1) and of the LCFS and RFS (SI section 3). Pathways P12 to P15 were not included in our previous study. We developed performance and cost metrics for these consistent with those in our prior study, as described in notes *g* and *h* of Table S2. All facilities are assumed to start operating by 2032 and have book lives of 15 years. We have assumed plants start up in the early 2030s because 1) IRA credits accrue only to a producer who commences construction by the end of 2032 and 2) the time available between today and 2032 seems sufficient for commercial projects to be launched by then.

We use a derating factor (DF) to account for the impacts of different policy durations (e.g., 10 years for 45V and 12 years for 45Q) over evaluated 15-year project lifetimes. A DF of 1 means that the provision is available during the entire project lifetime. DF is determined by Eqn (1),

$$DF = \frac{\sum_1^m (1/(1+r))^m}{\sum_1^n (1/(1+r))^n} \quad (1)$$

where r is the real weighted-average cost of capital (WACC), n is the book life of the facility (15 years), and m is the duration of the IRA provision (Table S1). A WACC value of 0.1 is used, as used in modeling H₂ and SLF production technologies by Jones and Haley in Annex A.2 of Net Zero America report¹³.

The LCOFs for hydrogen pathways are determined by Eqn (2),

$$LCOF_{p,H_2} (\$/kg) = \frac{CAPEX_p * CRF + FOM_p + VOM_p + F_p + Seq_p}{M_{p,H_2}} \quad (2)$$

$$- \frac{Max(M_{ccs,p} * 45Q_p * DF_{45Q}, M_{H_2,p} * 45V_p * DF_{45V})}{M_{p,H_2}}$$

where subscript p refers to a specific H₂ generation pathway (P1-P6), and $CAPEX$ is the overnight capital cost (\$) of the facility, CRF is the annual capital recovery factor (0.131), FOM is the annual fixed operating and maintenance cost (\$), VOM is the annual non-fuel variable cost (\$), F is the annual cost of feedstock (natural gas, electricity, or biomass) (\$), Seq is the annual CO₂ transport and storage cost (\$), M_{H_2} is the annual hydrogen production (kg), M_{ccs} is the annual CO₂ sequestered (tonne), $45Q$ is the tax credit for CCUS (\$/tCO₂ based on Table S1), DF is the derating factor (Eqn. 1), and $45V$ is the tax credit for clean hydrogen production (\$/kg, as in Table S1). Hydrogen product leaving the facility gate is at 30 bar. For all hydrogen production pathways other than electrolysis (P4), the final hydrogen product is delivered from pressure-swing adsorption (PSA) units, which typically operate at a pressure around 30 bar³². For P4, the hydrogen product is delivered directly from PEM electrolyzers, which are capable today of delivering H₂ at 30 bar³³. The capacity factor for H₂ routes is assumed to be 0.85, except for electrolysis, which is assumed to be 0.55 (see note 5 of Table 1).

The SLF output of P7 to P15 is assumed to 82% synthetic paraffinic kerosene (SPK) and 18% naphtha on a lower heating value basis. (See Table 1, note 7.) The 45Z credit is \$1.75/gal and \$1/gal for sustainable aviation fuel (SAF) and other types of clean fuels (e.g., synthetic diesel), respectively. Therefore, the 45Z tax credit for 1 gallon of SLF in our analysis is $1.75 * 0.82 + 1 * 0.18 = \1.62 /gal, before applying any DF value. 1 gal of SLF has a lower heating value (LHV) of 0.126 GJ. LCOFs of liquid fuel pathways are determined by Eqn (3),

$$LCOF_p \left(\frac{\$}{gal} \right) = \frac{CAPEX_p * CRF + FOM_p + VOM_p + F_p + Seq_p}{V_{p,SLF}} + \frac{M_{dac,p} * (P_{dac} - 45Q_{dac} * DF_{45Q})}{V_{p,SLF}} \quad (3)$$

$$- \frac{M_{co2, ethanol,p} * (45Q_{ccs} * DF_{45Q})}{V_{p,SLF}} - (EF_p * DF_{45Z} * 45Z) - RFS_p - LCFS_p$$

where subscript p refers to a specific SLF pathway (P7-P15), and $CAPEX$, CRF , FOM , VOM , Seq are analogously defined as for Eqn. 2, F is the annual cost of feedstock (\$, for biomass, ethanol, or H₂, where H₂ cost is determined by Eqn 2), V_{SLF} is the annual SLF production (gallons), M_{dac} is the annual external CO₂ from DAC (tonnes) used for SLF production, P_{dac} is the price of the CO₂ from DAC (i.e., 280 \$/t CO₂, note e of Table S3), $45Q_{dac}$ is the tax credit for CO₂ utilization from a DAC facility (i.e., 130 \$/t CO₂, Table S1), $M_{co2, ethanol}$ (tonnes) is the annual CO₂ captured from a corn-ethanol facility, $45Q_{ccs}$ is the tax credit for CO₂ captured and sequestered from corn-ethanol CCS facilities (i.e., 85 \$/t CO₂, Table S1), $45Z$ is the full tax credit for SLF production (i.e., 1.62 \$/gal), EF is the emissions factor for calculating the 45Z credit (Table S1), DF is the derating factor (Eqn. 1), RFS is the RIN credit SLF can receive under the RFS program (\$/gal, Eqn. S1), and $LCFS$ is the carbon credit under California's LCFS program (\$/gal, Eqn. S2). Carbon footprints for assessing 45Z credit values are statutorily determined using the GREET model, which uses LHV values by default³¹. Therefore, we convert the life cycle GHG emissions given in Table S4 to a LHV basis (kg CO₂/MMBTU_{LHV}) and use these to determine EF values. The capacity factor for all the SLF pathways is assumed to be 0.85.

The CAPEX, FOM , VOM , and energy conversion efficiency associated with all the pathways are given in Table 2. See Table S2 for supporting details, including data sources, assumptions, and calculations, Table S3 and Table S4 for input energy and materials prices and life cycle GHG emissions.

Table 2. Summary of evaluated hydrogen and SLF technologies. Parameter values here are given per unit of output capacity or output energy. Energy values are on a higher heating value (HHV) basis. IFI is input energy divided by output energy (HHV). Co-product is electricity for all the cases, and positive values are inputs; negative values are outputs. See SI Section 3 (Table S2) for supporting details.

	Technology	Input Feedstock Intensity (IFI) (GJ _{in} /GJ _{out})	Co-product (GJ/GJ)	CO ₂ capture rate (%)	CAPEX (\$/kW capacity)	Fixed O&M (\$/kW-year)	Variable O&M (\$/GJ)
H₂	SMR	1.23 (NG)	0	0	543	19	0.36
	SMR-CCS	1.26 (NG)	0.024	91.2	943	28	0.00
	ATR-CCS	1.2 (NG)	0.048	94.1	825	25	0.00
	Electrolysis	1.28 (electricity)	0	0	1407	16	0.00
	BG-H2	1.78 (biomass)	- 0.079	0	2482	44	3.89
	BGCCS-H2	1.78 (biomass)	- 0.023	87	2587	46	3.89
SLF	RWGS+FTS	1.47 (H ₂)	0	0	1004	27	0.73
	Integrated BioFTS	2.02 (biomass)	0	0	3826	77	5.15
	Integrated BioFTS-CCS	2.02 (biomass)	0	87	3944	79	5.15
	Ethanol-to-Jet	1.09 (ethanol)	0	0	258	26	2.15
	Ethanol with CCS-to-Jet	1.09 (ethanol)	0	0	258	26	2.15

Finally, Levelized Subsidies for CO₂ Mitigation (LSCM) implied in IRA credits for clean H₂ or SLF are determined by Eqn 4.

$$\text{Levelized subsidies of CO}_2 \text{ mitigation}_p \left(\frac{\$}{\text{CO}_2\text{e}} \right) = \frac{-NG \text{ Fee}_p + 45V_p + 45Q_p + 45Z_p + 45Y_p}{CI_{\text{fossil}} - CI_p} \quad (4)$$

For each pathway (p), the credits ($45V$, $45Q$, $45Z$, and $45Y$) and the methane emissions penalty ($NG \text{ Fee}$) are converted into \$/kg H₂ or \$/gal SLF of final product. CI_p is the lifecycle carbon intensity of the pathway expressed in kg CO₂e/kgH₂ or kg CO₂e/gallon liquid fuel. CI_{fossil} represents the carbon intensity of the fossil benchmark. For H₂, this is the CI of pathway P1 (11 kg CO₂e/kg H₂) and for SLF CI_{fossil} is 10.7 kg CO₂e/gal (representative of conventional jet fuel).

Results:

Hydrogen Production Pathways. Figure 1A displays hydrogen LCOFs, and corresponding life cycle GHG emissions.

Upstream natural gas supply chain emissions and uncaptured CO₂ result in life cycle GHG emissions for blue hydrogen pathways, SMR-CCS (P2) and ATR-CCS (P3), of 3.3 and 2.9 kg CO₂e/kg H₂, respectively. Hence, these two pathways only qualify for the lowest level 45V credit, i.e., \$0.6/kg H₂ (Table S1), and benefit more from taking the 45Q credit. The resulting LCOF of blue hydrogen via P2 SMR-CCS (\$1.24/kg H₂) and P3 ATR-CCS (\$1.16/kg H₂) are slightly lower than for the benchmark gray hydrogen (P1) (\$1.29/kg H₂). Hydrogen from electrolysis using solar- or wind-derived electricity has zero carbon emissions and so receives the maximum 45V credit (\$3/kg H₂), which reduces its LCOF to \$0.31/kg H₂, well below the cost of gray hydrogen. Hydrogen via P5 BGH2 has life cycle emissions of 1.3 kg CO₂e/kg H₂ due to upstream GHG emissions associated with biomass production, processing, and transportation. Thus, the 45V credit available in this case is \$1.00/kg H₂, and the LCOF is uncompetitive at \$3.09/kg H₂. Finally, hydrogen via the P6 BGCCSH2 pathway has negative carbon emissions because biogenic CO₂ is captured and stored. Unlike the case with SMR-CCS and ATR-CCS, the \$3/kg H₂ credit from 45V has a larger effect on LCOF than the \$85/t CO₂ credit from 45Q. Thus, we apply 45V credits and obtain a LCOF of \$2.22/kg H₂.

These results demonstrate that the IRA is likely to drive commercial-scale deployment of green and blue H₂. Hydrogen produced via BGCCSH2 (\$2.22/kg H₂) is less economically attractive than green or blue hydrogen and costs significantly more than gray hydrogen. The 45V hydrogen credit is a tiered

credit system but does not provide additional incentive for the negative-emissions that characterize BGCCSH₂. Thus, under the IRA, the economics of BGCCSH₂ could be improved by either limiting the size of CCS equipment to capture and sequester just enough CO₂ to claim the full 45V credit or by capturing all CO₂ and selling the excess (about 95% of the total captured) to other facilities for revenue if there is a market for biogenic CO₂. If pursuing the latter strategy, the revenue from selling biogenic CO₂ for a price of about \$45/t would bring the LCOF for BGCCSH₂ to the same level as for gray H₂.

Figure 1. **(A)** Levelized cost of fuel production (LCOF), where positive values are costs and negative values are revenues from co-product sales or IRA credits, and life cycle GHG emissions for benchmark (P1.SMR) and five lower emissions hydrogen production pathways. Methane emission fees are embedded in our assumed natural gas price for P1- P3, and 45Y clean electricity credits are embedded in our assumed electricity price for P4 (see Table S3). The life cycle GHG emissions for P1-P6 (assuming GWP₁₀₀ for non-CO₂ GHGs) are adopted from our previous analysis²², and 142 GJ_{HHV}/kg H₂ is used to convert from kg CO₂e/GJ_{HHV} in²² to kg CO₂e/kg H₂. IRA credits shown here are expressed as derated values to account for project economic lifetimes longer than the IRA-stipulated durations over which incentives are available, e.g., the \$1/kg H₂ and \$3/kg H₂ 45V credits are derated to \$0.8/kg H₂ and \$2.4/kg (See discussion around Eqn. 1 in Method.) **(B)** Levelized IRA subsidy values as a function of the life cycle GHG emissions reductions for clean hydrogen (P2-P6) versus the benchmark (P1).

For each of the hydrogen pathways, Figure 1B plots the levelized IRA 45V or 45Q incentive, expressed per kg of H₂ produced, against the pathway’s lifecycle GHG emissions reduction relative to emissions from the benchmark pathway (P1). One observes that the levelized IRA subsidy for each pathway is not uniformly proportional to its emissions reduction. In particular, the electrolysis pathway (P4) departs markedly from proportionality. One likely explanation for this discrepancy is that IRA credits have two objectives: emissions reductions from hydrogen production in the near-term and technological advancements to reduce clean hydrogen costs in the long term. As society seeks to reach net-zero emissions by mid-century, it seems unlikely that fossil fuel-based blue hydrogen pathways (P2 and P3) will play major roles in the long run. We thus conclude that IRA incentives for the P2 and P3 pathways primarily incentivize near-term emissions reductions and not technology development, a conclusion further buttressed by the fact that the reforming technologies at the core of the P2 and P3 pathways are commercially mature today, and there are at least two commercial-scale reforming projects operating with CO₂ capture and storage and several additional projects have been announced^{34,35}. In contrast, electrolysis (P4) and biomass gasification (P5 and P6) technologies are not yet commercially

mature and have potential for significant cost-reduction through further technology advances and learning. P4 and P6 also have zero or negative lifecycle GHG intensities and can thus play a key long-term role in net-zero emissions economies. One might logically expect IRA incentives for these technologies to thus include an emissions reduction component comparable to that for P2 or P3 plus an additional “technology policy” incentive to promote near-term technology advancement/cost reduction.

The slope of a best-fit line drawn in Figure 1B through the methane reforming pathways (P1 – P3) is \$76/t CO₂e reduced, which could be interpreted as the amount of IRA subsidy provided strictly for reducing emissions. Extrapolating this line to the larger reductions in CO₂e emissions characterizing P4, P5, and P6 highlights the fact that the IRA incentive for green hydrogen (P4), \$217/tCO₂e reduced, is nearly triple the level of incentive associated with emissions reductions alone. The additional IRA incentive aimed at spurring technological advancement/cost reduction in this case is \$141/tCO₂e reduced. Meanwhile, the total IRA incentives for H₂ for biomass gasification (P5) and BGCCSH₂ (P6) include negligible additional bonuses. It is difficult to know the full reasons the IRA authors included a large bonus incentive for electrolytic hydrogen and nearly no bonus for biomass gasification-derived hydrogen. A partial explanation may be that they considered electrolysis to be an inherently modular technology, whereas biomass gasification and CCS are not. Modularity is regarded as among the most important factors for enabling rapid cost learning³⁶, as evidenced by dramatic cost reductions and rapid market share gains of wind turbines and solar PV modules for electricity generation. Hence, a sizeable IRA bonus incentive for electrolysis is well aligned with the ambitious goals of rapid societal electrification coupled with deep decarbonization of the electricity sector. On the other hand, by providing only a negligible bonus incentive for biomass gasification w/CCS (P6), the pathway with the highest carbon mitigation potential, the IRA misses an opportunity to ensure early market deployment and scale-up of a technology that might also contribute significantly to rapid decarbonization and net-zero economy-wide-emission goals. If the IRA were to allow a biomass-hydrogen producer to earn both 45V credits for carbon-neutral hydrogen plus 45Q credits for negative biogenic CO₂ emissions, P6 hydrogen would be cost-competitive with gray (and blue) hydrogen with an LCOF of 0.84 \$/kg.

Synthetic liquid fuel pathways. The SLF production pathways analyzed in this work (P7-P15) have three basic configurations. P7 through P11 use a RWGS-FTS process taking clean hydrogen and carbon-neutral CO₂ derived from different processes (Table 1) as inputs, with hydrogen costs corresponding to the net LCOFs in Figure 1A. For P7-P9, the input CO₂ is assumed to be from DAC plants, and the IRA’s credit for DAC under 45Q is applied to the input CO₂ price, giving \$164/CO₂ (Table S3). Pathways P10 and P11 synthesize fuels using H₂ from P5 and P6, respectively, and carbon-neutral biogenic CO₂ recovered from the P5 and P6 facilities. The SLF costs for P10 and P11 incorporate 45V credits associated with P5 and P6 facilities, which are assumed to be adjacent to, but separate from, the SLF production facility. CO₂ separation is intrinsic to making hydrogen from biomass, and so it is assumed that the SLF producer incurs no extra cost for the CO₂, beyond what is reflected in the cost of the delivered hydrogen.

P12 and P13 pathways use biomass as input into integrated gasifier-FTS facilities, of which several configurations are under commercial development today³⁷. Note that pathways P10 and P11 represent another approach to using biomass to make SLF. The design of P10 and P11 is motivated strictly by the fact that the IRA disallows any one facility from claiming more than one credit: input H₂ from a dedicated biomass-to-hydrogen facility and CO₂ from the same facility (from the separated CO₂ stream) are combined and converted to SLF via FTS at a second facility. Each facility involved may claim an IRA credit, which effectively stacks two credits, whereas the biomass-to-SLF integrated single-facility configuration of P12 or P13 is eligible under the statute for, at most, one IRA credit.

P14 and P15 pathways are based on upgrading ethanol into SLF via dehydration of ethanol, oligomerization of the resulting ethylene into long-chain hydrocarbons, hydrogenation of the latter, and finally fractionation into desired fuels (e.g., naphtha and SPK)³⁸. It is assumed that the ethanol used for P14 and P15 is produced at standalone facilities.

Unlike our analysis for hydrogen (Figure 1), we include no direct liquid fuel subsidies in our LCOF calculations for SLFs for two reasons. First, the IRA's 45Z credit that would apply to SLF is stipulated to expire in 2027, and unlike 45V or 45Q, the credit does not offer a multi-year payment stream for projects eligible for the credit at the time they commence construction. Instead, payments from 45Z are made only for eligible fuels produced in the years the credit is in effect. Unless the credit is renewed and extended it will therefore not be available to any facilities operating in the 2030s. Second, the federal RFS and California LCFS have been important driving factors to promote the deployment of low-carbon fuels in the transportation sector, but both credits are subject to high uncertainty and volatility (Figure S1). Hence, we have chosen to exclude all three of these policies from our baseline scenario analysis and instead to explore the impact of these as a sensitivity later in this paper.

Figure 2 presents LCOF and life cycle GHG emissions for all the SLF pathways. Using electrolytic H₂ and CO₂ from DAC to synthesize liquid fuels (P9, or "electro-fuels") results in the lowest LCOF (\$2.9/gal). While higher than the median value of recent fossil jet fuel prices (\$2.2/gal), this estimated LCOF is within the recent historical range in jet fuel prices and may therefore prove competitive without any explicit liquid fuel subsidy, especially for customers with voluntary advanced market commitments to purchase sustainable aviation fuel³⁹. Fossil hydrogen based SLF pathways have much higher LCOFs at \$4.3/gal (P7) and \$4.2/gal (P8).

With bio-derived H₂ and CO₂ as feedstocks (P10 and P11) or with direct biomass feedstock (P12 and P13), LCOFs for SLF are generally higher, ranging from \$4.2/gal to \$6/gal. Comparing the two biomass-to-SLF approaches noted above, we find that SLF via P12 (integrated-gasification-FTS) and P13 (integrated-gasification-FTS with CCS) have higher LCOF than their corresponding 2-facilities pathways, P10 and P11, respectively. The single-facility configurations have lower CAPEX and higher energy efficiency than the 2-facilities configurations (see note g of Table S2), which means that the LCOF would be lower for P12 vs. P10 and for P13 vs. P11 in the absence of any subsidies. However, given the IRA's prohibition against a single facility earning more than one tax credit, it is economically preferable to pursue the more capital-intensive and less efficient process of producing hydrogen and CO₂ at one facility and producing SLF from the H₂ and CO₂ at a different facility in order to claim multiple IRA credits. This is concerning, considering that sustainable biomass feedstock is a limited resource. This finding is explored further in Section 5 of the SI.

As for GHG emissions for P10 and P12, where CCS is not part of the pathway, total GHG emissions are due only to upstream biomass production, transportation, and processing. Since the biomass-to-SLF conversion efficiency for P12 is higher than for the P10, less biomass input is required with P12 and the GHG emissions are correspondingly lower. When CCS is part of the process, as in P11 and P13, biogenic CO₂ is captured and sequestered, resulting in net negative lifecycle GHG emissions. In this case, the process that converts biomass to SLF with lower efficiency (P11) results in more byproduct CO₂ available for capture (and less converted to SLF) and thus has more-negative lifecycle GHG emissions than the more efficient pathway, P13.

Using ethanol to produce SLF (P14 and P15) results in moderate LCOFs (\$3.8/gal and \$3.6/gal) that straddle the historically highest price of jet fuel seen in the past decade. These LCOFs are higher than the LCOF of electro-fuels (P9) but are lower than that of other SLF pathways evaluated in this study. The life cycle GHG emissions of P14 are the highest among the SLF pathways, which is mostly due to emissions associated with corn-ethanol production, including emissions from corn farming and heat and electricity used for refining⁴⁰. Capturing the fermentation CO₂ (pathway P15) reduces lifecycle emissions by nearly two-thirds, bringing them down nearly to the level of emission for the biomass-SLF facilities without CCS (P10 and P12).

Figure 2. LCOF and life cycle GHG emissions (GWP₁₀₀) for SLF production pathways. The SLF product is assumed to consist of 82% synthetic paraffinic kerosene (SPK) and 18% naphtha on an LHV energy basis. (See Table 1, note 7.) The life cycle GHG emissions for P7-P11 are adopted from our previous analysis²², and converted to kg CO₂e/MMBTU_{LHV} shown here assuming a HHV/LHV ratio of 1.05. The life cycle GHG emissions of P12-P15 are determined using assumptions and methodology consistent with²². The left-most bar represents the range in annual-average wholesale petroleum jet fuel prices seen in the US from 2012 to 2022⁴¹. The median value was \$2.2/gallon. For P7-P11, the 45V and 45Q-CCS credits shown here are those that are incorporated in the LCOF of H₂ (Figure 1A), but expressed on a per-gallon of SLF basis, and the hydrogen cost plotted here is gross H₂ cost (i.e., with IRA credits excluded).

Sensitivity analysis: low-carbon fuel subsidies. For reasons noted earlier, our baseline SLF analysis excluded any consideration of 45Z, LCFS, or RFS credits. Here we explore how these subsidies might impact LCOF for SLF pathways.

To assess the impacts of extending 45Z into the 2030s, we determined the LCOF of each SLF pathway as a function of the 45Z duration, ranging from 0 to 15 years. Not surprisingly, longer durations yield lower LCOFs (Figure 3A). As noted earlier, the electrolysis-based pathway (P9), and the EtOHCCS-SLF pathway (P15), even without any 45Z credit, have LCOFs that falls within the recent historical price range for jet fuel. If the 45Z duration is at least two years, then bio-derived SLF (with H₂ and CO₂ from separate facilities, P11) also becomes competitive with historical jet fuel prices, while a 45Z term of five years or more would be needed to make bio-SLF at integrated facilities (P13) viable. The P11 pathway captures both 45V and 45Z credits, while P13 captures only a 45Z credit, which explains the lower LCOF for P11 than P13 at any given 45Z duration. Both P11 and P13 LCOFs fall rapidly with increasing durations of 45Z, because their negative lifecycle emissions (Figure 2) lead to very high 45Z credit values (Figure S2 and Eqn. S3). The P11 LCOF falls more rapidly than for P13, even though both pathways start with biomass and end with SLF produced. Because P11 has a lower overall energy conversion efficiency, the pathway captures more CO₂ per unit of SLF produced and so receives a larger 45Z credit than the more efficient P13 pathway. No other SLF pathways become economically viable with 45Z durations less than 15 years.

Figure 3. (A) LCOF for SLF production pathways as a function of 45Z duration. The shaded region represents the range in monthly average wholesale jet fuel prices in the U.S. from 2012 to 2022⁴¹: the lower bound is at the 10th percentile of the range (\$1.4/gal), and the upper bound is at the 90th percentile (\$3.72/gal). P14 is not shown on the graph because it is ineligible to receive 45Z and thus is insensitive to the duration of 45Z. (B) SLF production pathways that would be competitive with fossil jet fuel at 2.2 \$/gal under different 45Z durations, LCFS carbon credits, and RIN prices. All pathways (P7-P15) were considered in the analysis, but only P11, P12, P13, and P15 are competitive in the variable space examined here. P12 - P15 pathways are eligible for RIN credits (at 1.64 RIN credits per gallon). P14 and P15 are assumed to claim D6 and D5 RINs, respectively. Here we assume D6 and D5 RIN prices are the same. P12 and P13 are assigned D3 RINs, and the D3 price is the D5 price plus \$0.5 and \$1.5, which is the 25th and 75th percentile of the price difference between D3 RINs and D5 RINs in the past ten years. See Section 2 of the SI for discussion of RIN categories and prices.

In addition to 45Z, clean SLF may benefit from additional existing policies such as the RFS and LCFS, if these do not expire in the 2030s. Here we assume all pathways claim LCFS credits based on their carbon intensity (see Eqn. S2). The integrated biomass-SLF facilities (P12 and P13), and ethanol-SLF facilities may additionally claim Renewable Identification Number (RIN) credits under the category of cellulosic biofuel D3 (for P12 and P13), advanced biofuel D5 (for P15), and renewable biofuel D6 (for P14), as discussed in the Section 2 of the SI. Due to the uncertainty and volatility of RIN and LCFS credits (Figure S1), we examine LCOF values over a range of LCFS credit levels, RIN prices, and 45Z durations. Within this variable space, Figure 3B shows which pathways provide an LCOF competitive with a fossil jet fuel priced at \$2.2/gal, the median historical value during 2012-2022.

With the D5 RIN at \$0.75 and the D3 RIN at \$1.25 (upper left panel in 3B), fossil jet fuel is the least costly option when the LCFS credit is below \$25/t CO₂e and the 45Z duration is less than 2 years. The P15 pathway is the most competitive option when the LCFS credit is between \$25/t CO₂e and \$75/t CO₂e and the 45Z duration is less than 2 years. The P11 pathway outcompetes all others in the rest of the variable space. When the D5 RIN value is \$0.75 and the D3 RIN is \$2.25 (upper right panel in 3B), the P12 pathway is the most competitive one when the LCFS credit is below \$25/tCO₂e and the 45Z duration is less than 1 year. The P13 and P11 pathways become the dominant options for the rest of the parameter space (longer 45Z duration and higher LCFS favors P11). When the D5 RIN value is \$1.5 and the D3 RIN is \$2 (lower left panel in 3B), P15 pathway is the most competitive option when the LCFS credit is below \$100/tCO₂e and the 45Z duration is less than 3 years, and the rest of the parameter space is again dominated by P13 and P11. Finally, with D5 RIN at \$1.5 and the D3 RIN at \$3 (lower right panel in 3B), P12 is the most cost-effective option when subsidies from 45Z and LCFS are small, but P13 outperforms

all others across the rest of the parameter space. A wider range of D5 and D3 RIN values is explored in Figure S4.

Measuring IRA incentives against the Social Cost of Carbon. IRA incentives can be viewed as subsidies for achieving GHG emission reductions. In this context, it is of interest to express the incentives for each clean-energy pathway in terms of the Levelized Subsidy for Carbon Mitigation (LSCM, Eqn (4)) and compare these with recent U.S. federal government estimates of the Social Cost of Carbon (SCC) for the 2030 to 2040 timeframe⁴². The SCC is an estimate of the economic damages anticipated from climate change due to one additional tonne of CO₂ emissions. For this comparison, the amount of CO₂ mitigated by a pathway is taken to be the difference between the lifecycle emissions for the pathway and that for the pathway’s fossil benchmark. Figure 4 shows LSCM values for all clean-energy pathways, along with the range in estimated SCC for 2030-2040. For the SLF pathways, we assume the 45Z credit is extended and available for the full assumed asset life (15 years), representing a perhaps optimistic case for liquid fuel pathways. Credits from RFS and LCFS have not been considered in determining these LSCM values.

Figure 4. Levelized subsidy for carbon mitigation (LSCM) implied in IRA credits for all evaluated pathways. The assumed duration of 45Q, 45V/45Y, and 45Z/methane penalties are 12, 10, and 15 years, respectively. LSCM is the sum of IRA credits (\$/kg H₂ or \$/gal SLF) divided by the emissions avoided relative to fossil-derived hydrogen or liquid fuel. See Eqn (4). P14 does not receive any IRA credit. The indicated range in Social Cost of CO₂ emissions (SCC) is for discount rates from 1.5% to 2.5%⁴². For 2030 and 2040, the SCC ranges are \$140 to 380/t CO₂ and \$170 to 430/t CO₂, respectively.

LSCM values for four of the hydrogen pathways (P2, P3, P5, P6) are below the SCC range, and for one pathway (P4) it is in the mid-range of SCC values. Our earlier analysis (Figure 1A) showed that, with IRA credits, blue H₂ (P2 and P3) and green H₂ (P4) are cost-competitive with incumbent (gray) H₂. Figure 4 shows that their deployment, especially blue H₂, would be societally cost-effective as well, considering avoided emissions related damages. Our earlier analysis also showed that IRA credits for P5 and P6 pathways are insufficient to make these cost competitive with gray H₂. Figure 4 indicates that higher credits are justified from a societal perspective. For example, if 45Q credits were allowed for biogenic CO₂ sequestration with P6, as mentioned in our discussion of Figure 1B, the P6 pathway would be cost-competitive with gray hydrogen and the implied LSCM (\$130/t CO₂e) would still be below the lower bound of SCC.

Figure 4 shows that LSCM values for SLF pathways fall within or below the SSC range, except for the electro-fuel pathway (P9). Our earlier analysis (Figure 3A) showed that, with IRA credits (assuming a 15-year 45Z duration), the P9, P11, P13 and P15 pathways would be cost-competitive with the fossil liquid-fuel benchmark. Figure 4 shows that deployment in the case of P11, P13 and P15 pathways also would be cost-competitive from a societal perspective, but not in the case of P9, for which the LSCM is far above the SCC range. Furthermore, we previously suggested that it might be justified to incentivize negative-emissions by allowing the pathway P6 to claim 45V credits for low-carbon hydrogen production and, additionally, 45Q credits for negative (biogenic) CO₂ emissions. It would not be appropriate for a similar negative-emissions incentive to be applied for liquid fuels production, however, because 45Z credits are already linked to a pathway's carbon intensity, such that the credit increases as the emissions grow more negative (Figure S2). Thus, allowing a SLF pathway like P11 or P13 to earn 45Q credits and 45Z credits simultaneously would, effectively, be providing two incentives for the same negative emissions.

Discussion:

Our results provide insights on each of the research questions posed in the introduction.

First, our analysis demonstrates that IRA subsidies will enable clean hydrogen to be cost-competitive with gray hydrogen. Blue hydrogen will have costs comparable to gray hydrogen thanks to the 45Q credit for CCS. Green hydrogen receives the highest subsidies among all evaluated hydrogen pathways due to the combination of a 10-year 45Y renewable electricity PTC and a 10-year 45V hydrogen PTC, which make electrolysis the lowest cost option for hydrogen production. Biomass-derived hydrogen, however, is not cost-competitive despite IRA subsidies. In our analysis, we used attributional LCA⁴³ and determined that green hydrogen had zero GHG emissions (Figure 1A) when carbon-free electricity sources are used. However, green hydrogen may result in consequential carbon emissions, as when procurement of carbon-free electricity for hydrogen production leads other electricity users to switch to fossil generated power to meet their demands⁴⁴. This raises concerns regarding the environmental benefits of green hydrogen, at least until the grid is fully decarbonized. Further efforts on LCA methodology (e.g., attributional/consequential LCA selection, co-product accounting, and system boundary definition) are necessary to ensure electrolytic hydrogen has near-zero lifecycle emissions.

Second, our results indicate that IRA incentives favor the electrolytic route to hydrogen over others, because subsidies for different hydrogen production pathways are observed to be approximately proportional to their GHG emissions reductions (\$76 /t CO_{2e} reduced), while the electrolysis route receives a disproportionately higher subsidy (\$217/t CO_{2e}). This suggests the IRA is intended to incentivize technology innovation as well as emissions reductions in the case of green hydrogen. A similar technology policy rationale could also reasonably apply to biomass gasification routes to hydrogen, but this is not the case under current IRA provisions.

Third, for SLF pathways, we find that renewal and extension of the 45Z credit would be necessary for most low- and negative-carbon emissions SLF production pathways to be competitive with petroleum-derived jet fuels. The duration of a 45Z extension of 5 years would allow four clean SLF routes to achieve LCOFs that fall within the recent historical range in U.S. wholesale jet fuel prices, without considering the impact of any additional incentives (e.g., RFS or LCFS).

We also find that stacking 45V and 45Z credits by artificially separating production facilities, e.g., P10 and P11, provides for greater subsidies and results in a lower LCOF for SLF production from biomass than with standalone integrated facilities (P12 and P13), despite the higher capital costs and lower conversion efficiencies of biomass to fuel at separated production facilities. We further note that the IRA defines 45Z incentives to be a function of a pathway's life cycle GHG emissions. Accordingly, pathways with negative emissions receive the highest credits per gallon of fuel produced. This raises the possibility that 45Z credits by themselves may incentivize less energy-efficient (P11) over more energy-efficient (P13) bio-SLF production with CCS, because the lower efficiency enables greater CO₂ capture

and storage to achieve stronger negative emissions. When federal RFS credits (RINs), which are available only to stand-alone biomass-SLF facilities (P12 and P13 pathways), are stacked with 45Z credits, the P13 pathway could be sufficiently incentivized that it becomes more competitive than the P11 pathway. In addition, LCFS credits can be stacked with IRA credits for any of the SLF pathways. LCFS and RFS credits have historically fluctuated over time (Figure S1), and there is uncertainty around what they will be in the 2030s. For a wide array of combinations of 45Z duration, LCFS credit level, and RIN value, our analysis finds that the P11, P12, P13 or P15 pathway is the most cost-competitive one against the median monthly-average wholesale price of jet fuel over the past decade. No SLF pathway is competitive with \$2.2/gallon jet fuel for short 45Z durations combined with low LCFS and RIN values.

Finally, we find that IRA incentives for each pathway, when expressed in terms of LSCM, are below or within the range in the SCC estimated for 2030 to 2040, except for the electro-fuel pathway (P9), which receives a significantly higher total incentive due to stacking of multiple IRA credits. It is notable that, with IRA credits, BGCCSH2 (P6) is not cost-competitive with gray H₂ (P1), but has a LSCM well below the lower bound of the SCC range. If the IRA were to allow BGCCSH2 to simultaneously claim 45V credits for low-carbon hydrogen and 45Q credits for negative emissions, it would become cost-competitive with gray H₂, and the LSCM would still be below the lower bound of the SCC range.

In addition to the hydrogen and SLF pathways investigated in our analysis, one can envision other pathways to exploit stacking of credits to generate outside financial benefits, but with marginal environmental gains. For example, 45Y can be applied to carbon-free electricity generators to power electrolysis, 45V then provides \$3/kg H₂ to the electrolysis facility for its hydrogen production, and this hydrogen can end up in a hydrogen-fueled generator that could potentially claim a 45Y credit for its clean power generation. The system in this case intakes and produces carbon-free electricity, but the interior energy losses may be greater than another technology that performs the same service (e.g., battery electricity storage). For these reasons, policies that prioritize the use of fuels (hydrogen in particular) in sectors where there are no other alternatives or where decarbonization may be more challenging would be useful.

In general, we find that IRA achieves the objective of creating early commercial-scale deployment opportunities for emerging low-carbon hydrogen and liquid fuels technologies and pathways. Both green H₂ and blue H₂ pathways appear to be commercially viable under IRA incentives, while only modest extension of the 45Z clean fuels credit and/or incentives provided by the federal RFS or California LCFS make one or more SLF pathways cost competitive with historical fossil jet fuel prices. Accelerating market deployment of these clean fuels may not only contribute to near-term GHG emissions reductions, but also drive cost declines that enable deeper emissions reductions in the 2030s and 2040s both in the U.S. and around the world. However, we find the design of IRA tax incentives is likely to favor other pathways over those with the highest carbon mitigation potentials (H₂ from biomass gasification w/CCS and SLF from integrated biogasifier-FTS w/CCS), pathways that could prove to be critical options for achieving a net-zero emissions future.

Limitations:

Our work here is not without limitations, and we identify five key ones here that would benefit from additional examination in future work. (1) We have assumed that tax credits accrued throughout the supply chain will all be passed on to the final product (e.g., H₂ or SLF). For instance, in a project incorporating renewable generators for power generation and electrolyzers for H₂ manufacture, we assume that the full 45Y PTC value will go toward reducing the cost of electricity to the H₂ producer. In reality, the price of electricity to the H₂ producer will depend on competitive market dynamics or negotiated power purchase price. This could mean higher electricity costs to the H₂ producer. Liquid fuel pathways, especially eletrofuel, may be more complicated due to stacking of credits from multiple facilities. Although some entities, e.g., non-profit organizations, and projects claiming the 45Q credits (within the first 5 years of operation) are eligible to receive the IRA credits as “direct pay”, i.e., they

receive payments equivalent to the tax credits, a more common scenario may be to transfer to third-parties at some discount from full value. (2) We assume biogenic carbon to be carbon neutral. This generally holds for agricultural residues since they absorb CO₂ as they grow on an annual cycle, and they do not introduce new CO₂ into atmosphere when they are combusted. However, it may not apply for forest-derived biomass, which regrows on longer cycles. (3) For liquid fuel pathways we have evaluated Fischer-Tropsch and ethanol-to-SLF routes, but there are others that could monetize IRA credits and these would need to be evaluated to provide a more complete understanding of possibilities. (4) We did not differentiate our analysis of H₂ pathways by intended use of the H₂. In particular, we did not explicitly assess transportation use of H₂, which would likely require substantial new delivery and dispensing infrastructure to be established, but which might also qualify for LCFS and/or RFS credits. (5) IRA subsidies may very well alter the international competitiveness of clean H₂ and SLF produced in the U.S. We have evaluated chosen to examine only domestic competitiveness implications, but consideration of potential international implications would also be of interest.

Supporting Information: Detailed summary and interpretation of Inflation Reduction Act (IRA), Renewable Fuel Standard (RFS) and California’s Low Carbon Fuel Standard (LCFS) incentives; detailed summary of evaluated technologies; historical fuels and incentives prices; additional discussion of extending 45Z and complete design space of RIN credits; and comparisons of IRA credits and Social Cost of Carbon (SCC).

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Declaration of Interests:

J.D.J. is part owner of DeSolve, LLC, which provides techno-economic analysis and decision support for clean energy technology ventures and investors. A list of clients can be found at <https://www.linkedin.com/in/jessedjenkins>. He serves on the advisory boards of Eavor Technologies Inc., a closed-loop geothermal technology company, and Rondo Energy, a provider of high-temperature thermal energy storage and industrial decarbonization solutions, and has an equity interest in both companies. He also provides policy advisory services to Clean Air Task Force, a non-profit environmental advocacy group, and serves as a technical advisor to MUUS Climate Partners and Energy Impact Partners, both investors in early-stage climate technology companies. E.D.L. is on the advisory board and has an equity interest in DG Fuels, an emerging renewable hydrogen and biogenic synfuels company.

Author contributions:

Fangwei Cheng: Conceptualization, Investigation, Methodology, Formal analysis, Visualization, Writing – original draft; **Hongxi Luo:** Investigation, Formal analysis, Visualization, Writing – review & editing; **Jesse Jenkins:** Conceptualization, Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition; **Eric Larson:** Conceptualization, Investigation, Writing – review& editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition, Project administration

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